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To cite this article: Julian Quick *et al* 2024 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **2767** 092074

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Verification and Validation of Wind Farm Flow Models

Julian Quick¹, Rem-Sophia Mouradi^{2,3}, Koen Devesse⁴, Antoine Mathieu^{2,3}, M. Paul van der Laan¹, Juan Pablo Murcia Leon¹, and Jonas Schulte⁵

¹ Technical University of Denmark, Department of Wind and Energy Systems, Frederiksborgvej 399, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark

² EDF R&D, 6 Quai Watier, 78400 Chatou, France

³ CEREAs, École des Ponts, EDF R&D, Île-de-France

⁴ Department of Mechanical Engineering, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

⁵ Fraunhofer IWES, Küpkersweg 70, 26129 Oldenburg, Germany

E-mail: juqu@dtu.dk

Abstract. Wind farm flow models allow for the analysis of wind power plant wake effects. There are several mathematical models available to describe this complex flow, and some of them are implemented across multiple code bases. This manuscript presents a framework for verification and validation of these models of different complexities. As part of this work, an API was developed to interface the different flow tools using the WindIO wind plant schema. Then, verification techniques are applied to the embedded tools as a test to make sure there are no mistakes in the codes, and across different flow models. This reveals similarities and differences in stochastic trends given realistic measurement uncertainty. Validation is performed using a database of large eddy simulations to quantify model agreement with high fidelity data and develop a predictor of what this implies for future simulations.

1. Introduction

When wind turbines operate, they extract energy from the incoming air. The air behind the turbine has reduced energy and velocity. This region of air is referred to as the wind turbine wake. Wind turbine wakes are a major factor in the performance of wind power plants. The reduced energy in the wake results in downstream turbines receiving less energy, reducing the overall energy yield. Engineering wake models are often used to approximate wake dynamics when designing wind power plants. These models are typically represented analytically, in contrast to the more expensive Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) models that solve the Navier-Stokes equations in a discrete representation of the flow. Although CFD models may provide with more precise results for complex atmospheric conditions, engineering wake models are still preferred for design, because they take virtually no computational power to evaluate.

The wind energy open-source software community has created several implementations of different engineering wake models. A wake model is a mathematical tool that approximates the aerodynamic behavior of the flow in wind energy power plants. There is a spectrum of such flow codes with various levels of accuracy and complexity. Researchers are currently investigating blade-resolved flow simulations, offering an unprecedented level of detail in flow. Large Eddy

Simulation (LES) models use actuator line or actuator disc representations of turbines, and these implementations often take several days to run on large computing clusters. In an industrial setting, it is more common to use steady or unsteady Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) models or, more commonly, engineering wake models, which propose relatively simple algebraic representations of wind turbine wakes.

Model accuracy can be determined via verification and validation techniques. While verification and validation has been applied to some wind energy models [1, 2], these techniques are not common in the wind sector, and best practices have not been established. In this work, we consider verification to be the process of making sure computer codes run as expected and correctly solves the intended equations, and validation as the comparison between computer simulations and real-world data. Within the European Union (EU) project atmospheric Flow, Loads and pOwer for Wind energy (FLOW)¹, we have developed an Application Programming Interface (API) to run several wind farm flow models of different complexities using a common input schema, based on the WindIO ontology [3]. This API allows for many opportunities for verification and validation. For a similar approach based on low-fidelity models, see [4]. The presented API is a culmination of close collaboration within the FLOW project. Each supported tool is a product of the institutions represented within the project.

This manuscript approaches verification by comparing point predictions and sensitivity trends. It is expected that, when two codes implement the same model, the codes should yield the same results and correctly solves the intended equations. Verification of point predictions is then straight-forward. However, it is practical to apply other verification approaches when investigating two codes with different model assumptions. After all, both codes strive to model wind farm wakes. A probabilistic analysis can reveal the strengths and limitations of the different codes by highlighting their differences. In our case, we compare the sensitivity of different flow fields with respect to realistic measurement errors in the incoming wind.

It is not immediately obvious which wake model is appropriate to apply in different settings. It can not be taken for granted that more complex models will be more accurate. It seems likely that the different aspects of the relevant physics stressed by different models will drive the accuracy to different degrees under different flow conditions and farm configurations. We compare non-calibrated predictions of different wake models to a large LES dataset to see which model performs best under which conditions. These LES data are a stand-in for measured data, and we stress that true validation must be performed with measured data, by definition. The presented approach allows for the characterization, and eventually prediction, of model error when examining real-world data in future projects.

The remainder of this manuscript is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the four flow models embedded in the API. Section 3 explains the verification and validation methodologies employed in this study. Section 4 outlines the selected applications. Section 5 presents results and discussion, and the study is concluded in Section 6.

2. Flow Tool

Within the EU FLOW project, an open-source python Application Program Interface (API) is currently under development, embedding wind farm flow models of different fidelities. A schematic is shown in Figure 1. This includes engineering wake models, an Atmospheric Perturbation Model (APM), and 3D CFD, all of which allow to estimate the power production of wind farms. While the examined codes employ mathematical approximations of various complexities, they all aim to model the same physical phenomenon.

The objective of the FLOW tool is to make the use of these models harmonized and easier, although they are initially different both in formulation and use. In particular, this would allow

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101084205>

their absorption by industry, and chaining to other tools (e.g. load models). A python workflow is developed, and inputs and outputs are harmonized under the windIO standard [3] for four different tools (PyWake, FOXES, WAYVE, code_saturne). As FOXES and PyWake have many similarities, they are introduced in Section 2.1. Section 2.2 introduces code_saturne and WAYVE is introduced in Section 2.3.

Figure 1. Schematic describing the wake model API developed by the FLOW project.

2.1. FOXES/PyWake

The *Farm Optimization and eXtended yield Evaluation Software* (FOXES) is an open source wind farm and wake modelling framework by Fraunhofer IWES [5, 6]. It has been optimized for the fast evaluation of engineering wake models in the context of long-term time series of background fields and large wind farm configurations. PyWake is a modular code base developed by DTU [7]. It supports several engineering wake models and has interfaces to different CFD models. It is a part of the larger TOPFARM software suite.

These code bases implement several engineering wake models. Engineering wake models are sets of algebraic equations, which approximate the shape of turbine wakes using analytic functions. These models are categorized in terms of deficit, superposition, and velocity averaging approaches. FOXES and PyWake were used to benchmark different engineering wake models, as listed in Table 1.

ID	Description	Code	Coeffs	Superposition	Rotor av. bgd.	Rotor av. wake
b-14	Bastankhah 2014 [8]	PyWake FOXES	$k = 0.04$	Linear sum	Rotor center	Rotor center
b-14-ss	Bastankhah 2014, self-similarity blockage [7, 8, 9]	PyWake	$k = 0.04$	Linear sum	Rotor center	Rotor center
b-16	Bastankhah 2016 [10] Frandsen turbulence [11]	FOXES	$k = 0.04$	Linear sum Nearest wake	Vertical 20 Vertical 20	Grid 9 Top-Hat

Table 1. FOXES and PyWake model choices. Wake *Superposition* is either a linear sum of deficits or reduction to the wake from the nearest turbine. *Rotor av. bgd.* and *Rotor av. wake* refer to the computations of rotor effective background quantities and wake deltas, respectively. Here *Vertical 20* refers to rotor averaging over 20 points along a vertical line, and *Grid 9* averages wake effects over 9 points on a regular grid in the rotor plane, and *Top-Hat* evaluates the overlap of the the rotor and the wake circle areas. Notice that *b-16* applies two wake models with different superposition and averaging.

2.2. Code_saturne

Code_saturne is an open-source finite volume CFD solver for the Navier-Stokes equations [12]. It contains an atmospheric module solving the conservation of mass, momentum and energy,

here used with the assumption of incompressible and dry air. Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) with linear production $k - \varepsilon$ closure [13] is used to model the turbulence. The presence of wind turbines is accounted for using the Actuator Disk Model (ADM), i.e. a uniform and steady body force (thrust) locally applied by each turbine. The model setup embedded within the FLOW tool includes a circular computational domain centered on the farm automatically generated using the open-source SALOME platform (python scripts included in the FLOW Tool). The default domain is three times bigger than the farm and 800 m high. The minimal mesh element size is equal to $D/12$ at turbine positions and cell size progressively becomes larger away from the farm up to $0.8 \times D$ at lateral boundaries. These characteristics can be modified by the user through the python API. The Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) is parameterized by setting the system unknowns to a given vertical profile, at the domain boundaries and as initial state. If only the speed and direction at hub height are given, then the atmospheric profiles are extrapolated assuming a neutral stratification, using the Monin Obukhov Similarity theory [14].

2.3. WAYVE

WAYVE (Wind-fArm gravitY-waVes and blockagE) is an open-source framework that implements the Atmospheric Perturbation Model (APM) proposed by Allaerts and Meyers [15], based on earlier work by Smith [16]. The APM was developed to capture the mesoscale interactions between large wind farms and the atmosphere, without the computational costs of conventional mesoscale CFD simulations. Specifically, it focuses on the generation of wind-farm induced gravity waves in Conventionally Neutral Boundary Layers (CNBLs), and the blockage effect associated with these waves. To do this, the APM models the ABL as two height-averaged layers, and solves for the thicknesses of these layers, and the horizontal flow within them. The gravity waves above the ABL are incorporated through a pressure closure equation, that links their pressure feedback to the displacement of the capping inversion. As a simplified mesoscale model, the APM cannot resolve the flow at the turbine scale. Therefore, it is coupled to engineering wake models to compute the turbine inflow velocities. For a full derivation and description of the model, see Devesse et al. [17].

3. Methods

This section outlines the verification and validation methodologies employed. Section 3.1 discussed the statistical verification methods to verify different flow tools. Section 3.2 describes the validation metrics used in this study and suggests an approach for predicting model error.

3.1. Code Verification using Sensitivity Analysis

Verification helps assure that the FLOW tool adequately reacts to the user choices, meaning that it accounts for these choices accurately, does not ignore them, and raises exceptions if needed. In order to verify WAYVE, FOXES, pywake, and code_saturne, we submit these tools to uncertainty propagation and sensitivity analysis in a Monte Carlo framework. The idea is to generate samples of the physical variables (speed, direction, z_0) and track the sensitivity analysis of the flow and power as a function of location, similar to the work by Quick et al. [18].

Sobol' indices rely on decomposing the variance of the model output (e.g. power), generally denoted Y , into contribution terms due to the different uncertain inputs (e.g. incoming direction) generally denoted X_i . Normalizing the contribution terms by the variance of Y results on the Sobol' indices [19]. Formally, the first Sobol' index can be written as $S_i = \mathbb{V}(\mathbb{E}[Y|X_{\sim i}])/\mathbb{V}[Y]$, with $\mathbb{E}[Y|X_{\sim i}]$ the expectation of model values where only X_i is varied, and $\mathbb{V}(\mathbb{E}[Y|X_{\sim i}])$ is called the *partial variance*. This first Sobol index quantifies the ratio of the variance of the output variable explained by changes on variable X_i alone, i.e. it does not account for variance in the output that can occur when varying multiple variables including X_i . Sobol indices are widely used for generalized sensitivity analysis of non-linear model with independent uncertain

input variables. In this work the first Sobol indices are estimated using third order polynomial chaos expansions [20, 21].

3.2. Code Validation using Reference Data

The four flow models are validated by comparing turbine-specific power predictions to a reference dataset. We examine the well-known Root-Mean-Squared Error (RMSE) to quantify model accuracy. The RMSE quantifies errors predictions of each turbine power,

$$\text{RMSE} = \left[\frac{1}{n_t} \sum_{t=1}^{n_t} \left(P_t^{\text{obs}} - P_t^{\text{pred}} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}, \quad (1)$$

where n_t is the number of turbines, P_t^{obs} and P_t^{pred} are the observed and predicted power of turbine t respectively. This validation metric is used to quantify the agreement between each model and the observed data. Then, we develop a simple model error predictor based on a linear regression of the RMSE observed for a selected model versus the examined atmospheric conditions. The model with the smallest observed validation metric is used to fit a linear model,

$$\text{RMSE} = \vec{W} \cdot \vec{\psi} + b \quad (2)$$

where $\vec{\psi}$ is a vector of observed atmospheric parameters and \vec{W} , b are fit parameters and RMSE is associated with the flow model that yielded the lowest validation metric across all validation cases. The projection $\vec{W} \cdot \vec{\psi}$ is then used to construct a simple model error predictor.

Finally, we also investigate the performance of the different models with a physics-informed parameter. The LES cases are defined by their capping inversion characteristics and atmospheric stratification, which determine the behavior of gravity waves. The capacity of the models to capture these effects could relate to their performance across the dataset. Therefore, we investigate the prediction power of the non-dimensional group F_b ,

$$F_b = \frac{L}{H} \frac{U_b^2}{G^2} F_p, \quad F_p = \sqrt{\frac{Fr^{-4} + P_N^{-2}}{(1 - Fr^{-2})^2 + P_N^{-2}}}, \quad Fr = U_b / \sqrt{\frac{g\Delta\theta}{\theta}} H, \quad P_N = U_b^2 / NGH \quad (3)$$

where L is the wind-farm length, H is the height of the capping inversion, U_b is the average velocity within the ABL, G is the geostrophic wind, g is the gravitational acceleration, $N = (gd\theta/dz/\theta)^{-1/2}$ is the Brunt-Väisälä frequency, F_p is a dimensionless group describing the pressure feedback effect of gravity waves, Fr is the Froude number, and P_N is related to the pressure feedback of internal gravity waves. The group F_b has been found by Lanzilao and Meyers to correlate well with the pressure effects of gravity waves for the dataset considered here [22]. Any other physical effects are presumably mostly determined by the inversion height, since the velocity and momentum flux profiles are nearly identical for cases with the same capping inversion height. We therefore also include H as a second parameter.

4. Application

The FLOW API is used to perform verification and validation. The examined verification cases are presented in Section 4.1. The selected validation data is introduced in Section 4.2.

4.1. Verification

We selected simple one- and four-turbine verification cases for code verification. In both cases, we examine the DTU 10 MW reference wind turbine [23]. In the four turbine case, the turbines are spaced 7 rotor diameters apart in the eastern direction. These small wind farms do not have

the blockage effects WAYVE is designed to capture, and the tool boils down to the underlying engineering wake model. In future work, we plan to couple WAYVE with PyWake and FOXES. For these reasons, and for the sake of brevity, WAYVE results are omitted from the verification.

In both verification cases, FOXES and PyWake used the Bastankhah Gaussian wake model [8] (b-14 in Table 1), using the same wake model coefficients, no blockage, and the rotor center effective wind speed. The setting used for code_saturne simulations is the default one described in Section 2.2, and the same mesh is used for both verification cases, to avoid any mesh sensitivity.

Probability distributions were selected to represent realistic measurement errors. We assume normally distributed speed and direction errors, with standard deviations equal to 0.5 m/s and 3° , around nominal values of 10 m/s and 270° (westerly wind respectively). As it can be difficult to measure z_0 , we define a wide uniform distribution with bounds from 10^{-5} m to 10^{-2} m. While a log-uniform distribution may be more appropriate to sample a parameter that varies on such wide range, the uniform distribution is used for ease of presentation. Each distribution is independent of the others. These distributions are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Probability distributions and Monte Carlo samples used in the sensitivity analysis.

4.2. Validation

The reference data is described in Section 4.2.1. It is simulation data meant to be a stand-in for real-world observations. The flow model configurations used in the code validation are described in Section 4.2.2.

4.2.1. Validation Data The presented validation framework is applied to the examined wake models using the LES dataset from Lanzilao and Meyers [22]. These are all simulations of the same large wind farm, consisting of 160 IEA 10MW turbines with constant thrust and power coefficients, arranged in a staggered layout. As the dataset was developed to study blockage effects, the farm has a high power density of roughly 11.5 MW/km^2 , and a high thrust coefficient of 0.88. The farm is simulated in CNBL conditions, with variations in the characteristics of the potential temperature profile. In this study, we consider the cases with capping inversion heights H of 300, 500, and 1000 m, inversion strengths $\Delta\theta$ of 2, 5, and 8 K, and free atmospheric lapse rates $\gamma = d\theta/dz$ of 1, 4, and 8 K/km, leading to a total of 27 cases (see figure 3). These are denoted with H, C, and G respectively, so that the case H500-C5-G4 refers has $H = 500$ m, $\Delta\theta = 5$ K, and $\gamma = 4$ K/km. Note that these are the initial conditions for the profiles, and that these changed slightly during the precursor run. For a complete overview of the dataset, see Lanzilao and Meyers [22].

We stress that the LES data is a stand-in for measured field data, and as such has some artifices in both the idealized setup and the results. Notably for this study, all turbines used a constant thrust coefficient of $C_T = 0.88$, instead of a thrust curve as a function of the local wind speed. Additionally, the power as found by the LES solver has not been corrected with the Shapiro factor [24], and did account for air density. While this affects the specific power values, the trends across the different flow conditions should be realistic.

Figure 3. Speed (left), veer (middle) and potential temperature (right) vertical profiles from the 27 LES simulations constituting the validation data. Each validation case is represented by a shade of gray.

4.2.2. Flow Model Configurations This section describes the model settings when comparing the examined models to the validation dataset.

For `code_saturne` cases, user-defined inflow vertical profiles from the validation data are first given as an initial condition for a 1D single column model (precursor). The quasi-steady state results of the column model are then fed as initial and boundary conditions for the wind farm simulation. This ensures that the boundary conditions are already quasi-steady-state solutions that will be maintained across the numerical domain. Furthermore, considering the presence of capping inversions and stable temperature profile above the neutral boundary layer in the validation data, stratification effects such as the presence of gravity waves need to be accounted for. Compared with the default setup described in section 2.2, the minimal mesh element size is $D/10$, the domain height is extended to 25 km and 10 km large numerical sponge layers are activated to damp gravity waves and prevent their reflection on the domain boundaries.

The inputs for the APM are obtained by fitting the potential temperature profile [25], and processing the velocity and momentum flux profiles based on the resulting capping inversion height as described by Allaerts and Meyers. It is coupled to a Gaussian wake model [8] with the uni-directional wake merging method of Lanzilao and Meyers [26], using the velocity matching method developed by Devesse et al. [17]. A full description of the model setup can be found in Devesse et al. [17].

FOXES and PyWake were used to benchmark the three different engineering wake models from Table 1. For the model b-14 FOXES and PyWake are practically in agreement and predict nearly identical results at wind turbines.

5. Results

This section presents the verification and validation results, described in Sections 5.1 and 5.2 respectively. The model error predictor is also presented in Section 5.2.

5.1. Verification

This section compares uncertainty propagation results across FOXES, PyWake, and `code_saturne`. The mean and standard deviation are used to compare the point predictions of the different tools. Sobol effects indices are used to compare trends in model sensitivity to measurement errors. Section 5.1.1 presents a one-turbine case, which is the simplest setting to compare wake models. Section 5.1.2 presents a four-turbine case, where the turbines are aligned with the incoming flow, as a more complex case.

5.1.1. One Turbine Case The one-turbine case is a useful starting point for verification of engineering wake models. We examine the wind speed predicted by the different flow tools as a function of downstream distance. Figure 4 shows the mean and standard deviation resulting from

uncertainty propagation of the previously defined measurement errors, as well as the sensitivity analysis results. As expected, FOXES and PyWake give nearly identical results.

The FOXES/PyWake Bastankhah model predicts a more-extreme average deficit near the wake than code_saturne. As the wake recovers, the two models agree after 7 rotor diameters, with code_saturne predicting a slightly lower velocity (around 0.2 m/s of difference between the tools). The velocity values in the wake may however be sensitive to the choice of turbulence closure. Code_saturne predicts a steady increase in the standard deviation of the centerline velocity that starts dropping toward the nominal standard deviation after around 12 rotor diameters, while FOXES/PyWake predict a nonlinear pattern that returns faster to the nominal standard deviation. The higher code_saturne standard deviation may be due to the fact that the wake orientation is controlled by the direction, which generates stochastic fluctuations around the centerline, while PyWake and Foxes predict narrower wake deficit cones. However, the difference between the tools standard deviations remains reasonable, around 0.1 m/s.

Figure 4. Stochastic flow field associated with one turbine. Top left: Mean centerline flow field; Top right: centerline flow field standard deviation; Down left: Direction main Sobol index of centerline flow; Dwn right: Speed main Sobol index of centerline flow.

Regarding the Sobol indices, FOXES/PyWake and code_saturne have completely different sensitivity trends with respect to speed and direction. FOXES and PyWake model the wake as cone-like shape that expands as it convects downstream. The most extreme velocity deficit gradients are on the edge of this cone shape. As the wake propagates downstream of the turbine, centerline velocities become less sensitive to direction changes due to this assumed geometry. On the other hand, code_saturne models the wake using nonlinear equations, which generally reflect a sensitivity to direction that grows with distance downstream of the wake source.

5.1.2. Four Turbine Case A four-turbine layout is used to propagate the defined measurement uncertainties to verify behavior between the different flow tools. The distributions of powers predicted for each turbine, and the associated Sobol sensitivity indices, are shown in Figure 5. code_saturne predicts a slightly smaller wake deficit than FOXES/PyWake. The front turbine power predicted by code_saturne is slightly sensitive to the inflow direction because the inflow direction changes the blockage effect from downstream turbines. As the flow convects deeper into the array, all three codes show an increased sensitivity to direction.

5.2. Validation

The presented validation framework is applied to the examined wake models using the selected LES reference data set. We stress that the LES data is a stand-in for measured field data. Power predictions associated with the different models are compared to the LES validation data

Figure 5. Top: distribution of powers predicted by each FLOW tool. Bottom: power sensitivity analysis results.

in Figure 6. The simpler engineering wake models outperform the more complex models for low blockage situations, but the trend is inverted for higher blockage.

Figure 6. Power associated with model predictions and LES data plotted as a function of downstream distance. Each point corresponds to an individual turbine. The left panel shows a case with low blockage ($F_b = 18$) and the right panel shows a case with high blockage ($F_b = 62$).

The developed model error predictor is shown the left panel of Figure 7. There is a regime where RANS is the most accurate predictor and one where the 2016 Bastankhah model is the most accurate. This predictor can be used to anticipate the accuracy of future model predictions, suggesting the most accurate model to use under different atmospheric conditions. The RMSE is plotted as a function of the F_b quantity and inversion layer height in the right panel of Figure 7. The observed trends show that the 2016 Bastankhah engineering wake model agrees most with the validation data in situations with low blockage and low inversion height, while RANS yields the lowest errors when there is high blockage and inversion height.

6. Conclusions and Future Work

This study presents an API developed for the purpose of verification and validation of engineering wake models. We anticipate releasing this API as an open-source project next year, and hope to incorporate other wake modeling tools after we join the open-source community. Our framework is built on the foundation of the WindIO ontology, which allows for a flexible schema with unambiguous definitions that can be translated into the language of any flow tool. In future work, we plan to use this framework to further compare different FLOW models and to validate models against measured fleet data. There are still many open questions regarding how different atmospheric parameters influence the wind farm simulation tools available through our API.

Figure 7. (left): Model-specific RMSE as a function of projected atmospheric conditions, where the input parameters are normalized by their maximum values. (right) Model-specific RMSE as a function of F_b blockage quantity and inversion height.

Acknowledgments

This project is funded by the European Union Horizon Europe Framework program (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-04) under grant agreement no. 101084205. This work was developed based on collective efforts from all partners of the FLOW consortium.

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